

EFFECT OF IONIC LIQUID OR SURFACTANT ASSISTED BIOLOGICAL PRETREATMENT ON DELIGNIFICATION AND ENZYMATIC SACCHARIFICATION RATE OF RICE STRAW

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ABSTRACT

This study aim to enhance the biodelignification pretreatment of rice straw using laccase in the presence of ionic liquid ([AMIM]Cl) or surfactant (TritonX-100) due to increase enzymatic saccharification. Addition of [AMIM]Cl and TritonX-100 increases the lignin removal by 18.49% and 31.79%, respectively, which are higher than that of laccase only. The high lignin removal observed in TritonX-100 surfactant is accounted to its hydrophilic and hydrophobic sides which bind water and lignin, respectively, pulling the lignin into the water and enhancing its solubility. The enzymatic saccharification process was carried out based on four different strategies. The highest cellulose conversion was observed in the substrate was washed with distilled water after pretreatment of rice straw with laccase + TritonX-100 (40.96%), laccase + [AMIM]Cl (38.24%), and laccase only (37.91%) after 72 h of enzymatic saccharification. SEM, FTIR and XRD images suggest a rigid fiber structure of the untreated biomass and destruction of fibrous structure with roughness when it was pretreated. Enhanced saccharification on efficiency of rice straw was achieved by laccase pretreatment with ionic liquid or surfactant in a single system.

Keywords: *Enzymatic hydrolysis, Ionic liquid, Laccase, Surfactant, Pretreatment.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Lignocellulosic biomass (LCB) is renewable energy sources that can be converted to bioethanol. Moreover, it is a practical option for the improvement of energy security and reduction of greenhouse gas emissions. Rice straw is an abundant waste biomass worldwide with the potential to produce ~730 billion liters of bioethanol per year (Binod et al., 2010). To improve LCB conversion to

fermentable sugar, pretreatments have been developed to increase the accessibility of cellulase enzymes to cellulose. Biological pretreatments using microbes or enzymes have been extensively studied because they are inexpensive and require low energy input and mild environmental conditions, compared with other physico-chemical pretreatment methods (Mutschlechner et al., 2015). Laccase is a multicopper oxidase enzyme that oxidizes substituted phenols, a small percentage of lignin, using molecular oxygen as the final electron acceptor. However, this pretreatment process needs to be improved because of the low efficiency of bio-based delignification methods. Recently, several studies indicated that the combination of chemical pretreatment processes with biological pretreatment play as a key role in the decomposition of biomass and have attracted particular attention due to their great capability for increases the lignin removal and enzymatic digestibility. The application of ionic liquids (IL) and surfactants has been recommended to improve the pretreatment methods (Chang et al., 2016; Qing et al., 2010). However, the combination of ILs or surfactants with a biodelignification process has not been reported in a single system.

The objective of this study was to enhance the biodelignification pretreatment of rice straw using laccase (*Trametes versicolor*) in the presence of [AMIM]Cl or TritonX-100. The concentrations of [AMIM]Cl and TritonX-100 for high lignin removal were also investigated. The effect of the pretreatment was evaluated by performing enzymatic saccharification using different strategies. The changes in morphology, composition, and structure of the pretreated and untreated rice straw were characterized by scanning electron microscopy (SEM), Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR), and X-ray diffraction (XRD).

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Materials

In this study, rice straw was obtained from the Jimei District, Xiamen City, Fujian Province, China. The rice straw were pulverized and passed through 40 Mesh sieve. They were dried for 24 h at 60 °C and stored in a tightly sealed bag. Laccase prepared from fungus *T. versicolor* was purchased from Sigma (St. Louis, Mo, USA). Polyethylene Glycol Octylphenol Ether (TritonX-100) was purchased from Shanghai Aladdin Co. Ltd., China; [AMIM]Cl was purchased from Shanghai Monils Chem. Eng. Sci. & Tech. Co. Ltd., China. All experiments were carried out three times under the same conditions.

2.2 Rice straw pretreatment

Rice straw (0.5 g) was pretreated with laccase only (2U/g substrate), laccase with [AMIM]Cl (100–1000 mg/L) or TritonX-100 (100–1000 mg/L) by total volume for reaction is 10 mL. We also test with others ionic liquids and surfactants, the optimum condition is [AMIM]Cl and TritonX-100 (data not shown). The pretreatment was carried out in flasks incubated at 50 °C using a shaking incubator operating at 150 rpm for 24 h. Pretreated materials were washed with deionized water until the pH 7.0 and dried at 60 °C for 24 h. Solid recovery and composition of the untreated and pretreated rice straw were analyzed as described by Jung et al., (2015).

2.3 SEM analysis

The morphologies of untreated and pretreated rice straw were determined using a scanning electron microscope (SEM; JSM-7001F, JEOL Ltd., Japan). After freeze-drying, the samples were carefully mounted on the powder sample stubs using a double-sided carbon tape and 30 nm-thick conductive gold coating was applied to the surface. Images were acquired with a 15 kV acceleration voltage.

2.4 FTIR analysis

The structural characteristics of untreated and pretreated rice straw were determined using an FTIR spectrometer (Nicolet 6700, Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA) in the range of 400–4000 cm⁻¹ with 20 scans at a resolution of 4 cm⁻¹.

2.4 XRD analysis

X-ray diffractograms of untreated and pretreated rice straw were obtained with a X-ray diffractometer (D/MAX-2400, Rigaku, Japan). The sample was scanned in the range of 5°–40° (2θ) with a step size of 0.02° and step time of 1 s at 40 kV, 20 mA, and ambient temperature. The crystallinity index (CrI) of the samples was calculated with the following equation (Zhang et al., 2017):

$$CrI (\%) = \frac{I_{002} - I_{am}}{I_{002}} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

where I_{002} is the maximum intensity of the crystalline portion and I_{am} is the intensity of the amorphous portion.

2.5 Enzymatic saccharification

A total of 2.5% (w/v) pretreated and untreated rice straw was suspended in 0.1 M sodium citrate buffer (pH 4.8) with 0.02% sodium azide to prevent microbial growth, a cellulase complex (Novozyme NS220086, 250 FPU mL⁻¹) enzyme load of 50 FPU/g-solid substrate and β-glucosidase (Novozyme NS221118, 320 CBU mL⁻¹) enzyme load of 40 CBU/g-solid substrate, respectively. The pretreated rice straw was hydrolyzed in a horizontal shaker incubator for 72 h at a constant temperature of 50 °C and an agitation rate of 150 rpm. A sample was collected at 24 h, 48 h and 72 h, and centrifuged at 10000 rpm for 10 min. The total reducing sugar was determined via the 3,5-dinitrosalicylic acid (DNSA) method (Miller, 1959). The absorption was measured at 575 nm using a UV-Vis spectrophotometer (UV 756CRT, Youke Co., Ltd, China). Four parallel experimental conditions were determined before the enzymatic saccharification step: (1) filtration and wash with distilled water until pH 7.0 than dried at 60 °C for 24 h, (2) the pretreated rice straw was boiled at 100 °C for 20 min to deactivate laccase, (3) the pretreated rice straw was not filtrated and washed, and (4) simultaneous laccase pretreatment and enzymatic saccharification. The cellulose conversion was calculated as following equation (Palavesam, 2015):

$$\text{Cellulose conversion (\%)} = \frac{\text{Reducing sugar (g/L)} \times 0.9}{\text{Holocellulose}} \times 100 \quad (2)$$

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Effect of laccase and laccase with IL or surfactant pretreatment on the rice straw delignification

The lignin content was removed via laccase, [AMIM]Cl and TritonX-100 in this study. The lignin removal was calculated as following equation (Gong et al., 2015):

$$\text{Lignin removal (\%)} = 1 - \frac{\text{Lignin in the pretreated RS}}{\text{Lignin in the native RS}} \times 100 \quad (3)$$

The effect of [AMIM]Cl and TritonX-100 concentrations on the lignin removal during laccase pretreatment is shown in Figure 1. The lignin content gradually decreases with increasing [AMIM]Cl and TritonX-100 concentrations. The highest lignin removal, 31.79% and 18.49%, was observed when 500 mg/L TritonX-100 and 750 mg/L [AMIM]Cl, respectively, were added. The surfactant has both hydrophilic and

hydrophobic side and can bind to both lignin (hydrophobic side) and water (hydrophilic side) by pulling the lignin into the water and enhancing its solubility (Qing et al., 2010). Hence, the addition of surfactant was effective to delignification and improves the lignin removal. In addition, IL is also capable of lignin removal, which might have practical advantages for the enzymatic saccharification of cellulose. Thus, the 750 mg/L and 500 mg/L concentrations of [AMIM]Cl and TritonX-100, respectively, were selected for subsequent experiments.

Fig. 1. Effect of IL and surfactant concentrations on biological lignin removal efficiency. (a) TritonX-100 concentrations and (b) [AMIM]Cl concentrations. The different letters above the bars in figure indicate significantly difference at $p \leq 0.05$.

The pretreatment of rice straw with laccase only, laccase + [AMIM]Cl, or laccase + TritonX-100 led to an effective lignin removal of 11.96%, 18.49%, and 31.75%, respectively. Adding 500 mg/L TritonX-100 generated the highest lignin removal, enhancing it by 22.52%, compared with the sole laccase pretreatment. Results strongly support the enhancement of IL or surfactant on lignin removal. However, at a sufficiently high concentration of the TritonX-100 (750 mg/L and 1000 mg/L) was significantly decreased the percentage of lignin removal, it might become inhibitory by binding up the substrate (laccase enzyme) doesn't move freely and/or protein in micelles.

3.2 Effect of laccase and laccase with IL or surfactant pretreatment on rice straw composition

The chemical compositions of rice straw before and after laccase-only, laccase with IL, or surfactant pretreatment are summarized in Table 1. The untreated rice straw consists of 31.73% cellulose, 23.21% hemicellulose, and 15.79% lignin. The pretreatment of rice straw with laccase only, laccase + [AMIM]Cl, or laccase + TritonX-100 led to an effective lignin removal of 11.96%, 18.49%, and 31.75%, respectively, compared with untreated rice straw. However, [AMIM]Cl is less effective in removing lignin than TritonX-100. Adding 500 mg/L TritonX-100 generated the highest lignin removal, enhancing it by 22.52%, compared with the pretreatment with laccase only. These results indicate that the addition of IL and surfactant could enhance the lignin removal due to the reasons mentioned above. Additionally, this process also removes the hemicellulose content, which is 21.67%, 21.24%, and 19.66% after pretreating rice straw with laccase only, laccase + [AMIM]Cl, and laccase + TritonX-100, respectively, compared with untreated rice straw. However, hemicellulose removal increases the surface area and reduces unproductive enzyme binding and therefore increases the probability of cellulose to be hydrolyzed (Jeoh et al., 2007). The cellulose content is 38.50%, 39.57%, and 40.83% after pretreating the rice straw with laccase only, laccase + [AMIM]Cl, and laccase + TritonX-100; it increased due to the partial removal of lignin and hemicellulose.

Table 1. Chemical composition of untreated and pretreated rice straw.

Pretreatment	Cellulose (%)	Hemicellulose (%)	Lignin (%)
Untreated	31.73 ± 0.02	23.21 ± 0.03	15.79 ± 0.01
L	38.50 ± 0.02	21.67 ± 0.03	13.90 ± 0.01
L+[AMIM]Cl	39.57 ± 0.02	21.34 ± 0.04	12.87 ± 0.01
L+TritonX-100	40.83 ± 0.02	19.66 ± 0.04	10.77 ± 0.01

3.3 Effect of laccase and laccase with IL or surfactant pretreatment on enzymatic saccharification based on different strategies

To compare the effect of different pretreatment types on the enzymatic saccharification based on different strategies, the enzymatic saccharification was performed at an enzyme load of 50 FPU/g substrate and 40 CBU/g substrate at 50 °C for 72 h. Figure. 2 displays the percentage of cellulose conversion for untreated and pretreated rice straw with laccase only, laccase + [AMIM]Cl, and laccase + TritonX-100 using four

strategies of enzymatic saccharification. Laccase pretreatment significantly increases the cellulose conversion efficiency compared with untreated rice straw. The highest cellulose conversions, 40.96%, 38.24%, and 37.91%, were obtained after 72 h of enzymatic hydrolysis when the substrate was washed with distilled water after laccase + TritonX-100, laccase + [AMIM]Cl, and laccase only pretreatment, respectively (Fig. 2a). Figure 2 shows the cellulose conversion via the non-filtered substrate and washed before enzymatic hydrolysis (Fig. 2c) and simultaneous pretreatment and enzymatic saccharification (Fig. 2d) after 72 h of enzymatic saccharification. The cellulose conversion increased to 25.58% (laccase + TritonX-100), 24.95% (laccase + [AMIM]Cl, and 24.51% (laccase only) when the laccase was deactivated at 100 °C for 20 min (Fig. 2b). This result indicates that the laccase might be inactive during pretreatment or inhibited by enzymatic saccharification. Although the cellulose conversion increased by deactivating the laccase, it is still lower than the yield obtained from substrate washed with distilled water because some of the compounds generated via lignin degradation caused a decrease in the cellulose conversion yield. Therefore, the higher cellulose conversion yield using washed substrate indicates that there are enzyme inhibitions associated with pretreatment that can be removed by washing.

Fig. 2. Profiles of enzymatic hydrolysis from rice straw pretreated by laccase with [AMIM]Cl or TritonX-100 and hydrolyzed with cellulase complex (50 FPU/g RS) and β -glucosidase (40 CBU/g RS) by four enzymatic saccharification strategies: (a) The pretreated rice straw was filtered, washed with distilled water until pH 7.0 and dried at 60 °C, for 24 h. (b) The pretreated rice straw was boiled at 100 °C for 20 min to deactivate laccase, and the enzymatic hydrolysis was carried out after it cooled. (c) The pretreated rice straw was not filtered or washed before enzymatic hydrolysis. (d) Simultaneous laccase

pretreatment and enzymatic hydrolysis were conducted together.

3.4 SEM

The morphologies changes of untreated and pretreated rice straw were analyzed using SEM images (Fig. 3). The untreated rice straw exhibits a smooth and rigid surface structure, whereas the surfaces of the pretreated rice straw with laccase only, laccase + [AMIM]Cl, and laccase + TritonX-100 are broken into separated fibers or fiber bundles and cracks occur on different levels because of the removal of lignin and hemicellulose (Zhao et al., 2008). During further laccase + [AMIM]Cl and laccase + TritonX-100 pretreatment, the surface morphology of the rice straw became looser with a wider separation of the fibers than that of rice straw pretreated with laccase only because most of the lignin and residual hemicellulose were removed during laccase and IL or surfactant pretreatment. The removal of both hemicellulose and lignin resulted in the release of a larger specific surface area, which favors the following enzymatic saccharification.

Fig. 3. SEM images of untreated and pretreated rice straw. (a) Untreated rice straw, (b) laccase only, (c) laccase + [AMIM]Cl, (d) laccase + TritonX-100.

3.5 Characterization of the untreated and pretreated rice straw

FTIR and XRD spectra were obtained to monitor the changes of the chemical functional groups and the cellulose crystallization degree in rice straw (Fig. 4a and b). The bands at 3405 and 2917 cm^{-1} representing the O–H and C–H stretching vibration confirm the appearance of the lignocellulosic matrix in both untreated and treated materials (Oh et al., 2005). The spectra of all pretreated solids show the strongest absorption band at $\sim 1035 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. This band corresponds to the C–O stretching vibration in both cellulose/hemicellulose and lignin (Naik et al., 2010).

The band at 897 cm^{-1} attributed to the β -glycosidic linkages between monosaccharide units increased in all treated samples, suggesting a higher exposure of cellulose because hemicellulose was extensively

removed in the pretreatment. Moreover, the bands at 1370 and 1430 cm^{-1} also increased in all treated samples, which are associated with typical features of cellulose. The band at 1370 cm^{-1} corresponds to the bending vibration of $-\text{CH}$ and stretching vibration of $\text{C}-\text{O}$. The band at 1423 cm^{-1} corresponding to the bending of $-\text{CH}_2$ groups can be assigned to $-\text{C}-\text{CH}_2-$ of cellulose (Jiang and Hsieh, 2013). The band at 1732 cm^{-1} , representing the $\text{C}=\text{O}$ stretching vibration of hemicellulose acetyl, reflects the hemicellulose content. After laccase-only, laccase + [AMIM]Cl, and laccase + TritonX-100 pretreatment, this band exhibited a declined absorbance, suggesting that parts of the hemicellulose degraded (Zhang et al., 2012). The characteristic lignin bands at 1206 cm^{-1} (syringyl ring and $\text{C}-\text{O}$ stretching vibration), 1320 cm^{-1} ($\text{C}-\text{O}$ stretching vibration), 1548 cm^{-1} (aromatic skeleton $\text{C}-\text{C}$ stretching vibration in lignin), and 1610 cm^{-1} ($\text{C}=\text{C}$ stretching vibration) were less intense in the spectra of laccase-only, laccase + [AMIM]Cl, and laccase + TritonX-100 treated samples in comparison with the untreated rice straw.

Fig. 4. Spectrum analysis of rice straw under different pretreatment conditions. (a) FTIR spectra. (b) X-ray diffraction spectra.

The crystallinity of cellulose is considered to be major factor influencing the enzymatic saccharification because amorphous cellulose can be hydrolyzed enzyme-tically much more rapidly than crystalline cellulose. The XRD profiles for untreated and pretreated rice straw exhibit typical diffraction peaks at approximately $2\theta = 16^\circ$ and 22.6° , which confirms that the crystal lattice type I of native cellulose was

preserved, although it went through a series of treatments. The CrI value can be calculated base on Eq. (1). The low CrI value reflects a high amount of amorphous cellulose in the pretreated solids (Kou and Lee, 2009). All rice straw pretreated with laccase only (66.17%), laccase + [AMIM]Cl (64.71%), and laccase + TritonX-100 (64.58%) has a lower CrI than untreated rice straw (Table 2). The results confirm that the rice straw regenerated from laccase + TritonX-100 pretreatment exhibits the highest surface area, which is accessible to enzymes.

Table 2. Crystallinity index and size of untreated and pretreated rice straw.

Pretreatment	LOI (A_{1424}/A_{896})	TCI (A_{1368}/A_{2900})	CrI (%)
Untreated	1.5955	1.2423	67.85
L	1.5774	1.2282	66.17
L+[AMIM]Cl	1.5746	1.1976	64.71
L+TritonX-100	1.5689	1.1947	64.58

5. CONCLUSIONS

In this study, IL and surfactant were used to enhance the performance of laccase with respect to pretreated rice straw. The highest cellulose conversion was 40.96% and 38.24% using a combined pretreatment with laccase + TritonX-100 (500 mg/L) and laccase + [AMIM]Cl (750 mg/L), respectively, after 72 h of enzymatic sacchrification when the substrate was washed with distilled water. After laccase + [AMIM]Cl and laccase + TritonX-100 pretreatment, notable morphological changes were observed due to the increased specific surface area of rice straw. These results suggest that IL and surfactant can enhance the pretreatment performance of laccase and enzymatic saccharification.

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